

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE STUDY OF FEMINISTS

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to an integrated approach and analysis of derived units, involving a combination of analysis of feminines, their derivational structure and motivational relationships with the determination of the specifics of functioning in speech.*

Keywords: *feminities, development, professions, colloquial speech, written speech, suffix, rules.*

Introduction. Linguistic categories are recognized as the highest form of manifestation of systematicity in language, therefore the problem of their identification and description remains one of the central tasks of linguistics. The study of the linguistic structure in the categorical aspect requires something that is relevant for linguistics of the 21st century. functional approach, which involves combining semasiological analysis of linguistic units with subsequent onomasiological generalization - from function, meaning to the means of its expression, form. Meanwhile, the system of word formation of the Russian language, most fully described in the academic “Russian Grammar”, is presented in it as a set of word-formation types - formal semantic units, that is, fully comprehended from the standpoint of the systemic-structural paradigm of linguistics. Against the background of the dominant functional vector in grammar, this is regarded by many leading linguists as a significant lag in word formation in this aspect from other branches of Russian studies, as an obvious research gap that requires the priority attention of derivatologists.

The doctrine of language as a system was developed in the works of the student I.A.Baudouin de Courtenay N.V.Krushevsky, who writes that suffixes can express shades of meaning, citing diminutives as an example (suffixes -ик: дом - домик), also suffixes, denoting baby animals (suffix -онок: котенок, медвежонок, утенок, suffix -оныйш: утеныш). He reveals the connection between the meaning of a suffix and its ability to be isolated: “The ability of a suffix to be isolated is inversely proportional to the breadth of its meaning and the number of suffixes related to the given meaning.

“This important remark actually leads us to the formulation of a criterion for identifying a word-formation category on the basis of a word-formation device that realizes only this word-formation meaning. Reflections N.V. Krushevsky, in which he analyzes the meaning of word-forming affixes, correlate with the idea of categorization of language, which is the basis of modern cognitive linguistics.

A well-known representative of the Kazan linguistic school V.A.Bogoroditsky, also postulates the idea of systematic language, calling language not just a means of expressing thoughts, but an instrument of thought: “Adapting to developing thought, it also serves as an indicator of the success of the classifying activity of the mind.” The scientist writes about form formation as an intuitive process based on the categories of language already formed in our minds: “In our native language, from childhood we get used to the types of inflection, according to which we form the

required forms from these words; therefore, we do not remember all the forms from each word separately, but we ourselves produce them by analogy to the learned corresponding types.” Equally, this thought of V.A. Bogoroditsky is also true in relation to the categories of word formation, the models of which form a certain “word-formation habit” among native speakers in the formation of new words according to already existing models. The undoubted merit of V.A. Bogoroditsky is that he was the first to formulate and describe the categorical word-formation model of a noun in the onomasiological aspect.

The concept of a word-formation category receives a powerful impetus for development in connection with the accumulation of factual knowledge in this area and the rooting of anthropocentrism ideas in science and becomes the object of study in subsequent works on Russian grammar. Academician V.V. Vinogradov writes that the grammatical category of the person of a noun is differentiated with the help of various word-formation types, and therefore “in the sphere of word-formation, active processes of abstraction from the particular and concrete, processes of the formation of general word-formation categories are observed.” Subsequently, scientists were presented with a detailed holistic description of the system of Russian substantive word production as a set of word-formation types in the “Grammar of the Russian Language”.

The word-formation category acts as the main unit of word formation in the work of the Czech linguist M. Dokulil: “This is a more general concept than the word-formation type. It differs from the word-formation type in that it is abstracted from the unity of the formant.” M. Dokulil was the first to identify the main types of semantic relations of the producing and derived words, which became the basis for the organization of the word-formation system: mutational, modification and transposition.

The names of female persons can be motivated by different types of bases and have different word-formation meanings according to the nature of the connection with the motivating base. Thus, the semantics of words with mutational meaning is completely different from the semantics of the generating word, forming a new conceptual content: 'female person, producing action, called the motivating basis' (гадать - гадалка), 'wife of the person named motivating basis' (генерал - генеральша). The semantics of words with a modification meaning only supplements the meaning of the motivating word with an additional feature 'лицо' (“face”) - 'female person' without changing the basic conceptual content (teacher - teacher, smart guy - smart girl). However, in derivatology, these terms are interpreted ambiguously; in addition, some scientists identify so-called mixed-type categories.

V.V. Lopatin identifies secondary, complex categories in which simple meanings, mutational and modification, are combined, and calls them mixed categories. As an example, the scientist cites the derivatives reaper, witch, seamstress, cook, twitter, which, in his opinion, combine the mutational meaning “producer of action” and the modification “femininity.” However, the onomasiological approach assumes a view of the word-formation meaning as “the meaning of the model as a whole”. The names of female persons, formed from verbal, adjectival and substantive bases, do not have a formal semantic connection with masculine personal nouns due to the absence of a corresponding phenomenon in the real world. An attempt to divide the word-formation meaning into two components, based on the incompleteness of the word-formation chain of these derivatives, is a formalist step that does not correspond to the cognitive nature of the modern approach to word formation as a way of expressing linguistic consciousness and mentality. It seems appropriate to consider such derivatives exclusively as mutational,

undergoing inter-unit transformation and forming a new concept corresponding to the phenomenon of the objective world.

The essence of the word-formation category in terms of the field is conceptualized in the monograph by O.G.Revzina “The structure of word-formation fields in Slavic languages.” The concepts of a word-formation category and a word-formation field are identified by the researcher: “Each suffix in the agent field has the same agent meanings as the entire field,” which corresponds to the idea of a word-formation category as a set of word-formation means that have the same word-formation meaning as the word-formation itself. category.

Individual word-formation categories of the Russian language or a certain combination of them have become the object of deep functional-semantic research (E.S. Kubryakova, I.S.Ulukhanov, E.A.Zemskaya, R.S.Manucharyan). We will proceed from a general definition, the essence of which boils down to the fact that a word-formation category is characterized by the unity of word-formation meaning despite the difference in means of expression.

Monograph by Y.S.Azarkh “Word formation and morphology of nouns in the history of the Russian language” (1984) is an important study of word formation in the aspect of historical derivational morphology. Y.S.Azarkh considers the problem of the connection between morphological word formation and grammatical categories of a noun - gender, animate/inanimate, number, as well as the interaction of word-formation types of a noun in the 11th - 13th centuries. In the 90s XX century in works on Russian derivatology, interest in the concept of word-formation category continues to grow (V.M.Gryaznova, Y.G.Kadkalov, E.P. Kadkalova, E.B.Nazarova, T.V.Shkvartsova).

At the beginning of the 21st century. the theory of word-formation categories received its coverage in the reports of the II International Congress “Russian Language: Historical Destinies and Modernity” (2004), as well as the III International Congress (2007), the VIII International Conference of the Commission on Slavic Word Formation under the International Committee of Slavists “Categories of Language and Word Formation” (2005). Cognitive Research the peculiarities of certain categories of the Russian language, as well as the understanding of the experience of onomasiological modeling of the Russian derivational system accumulated by word formation was an incentive for the subsequent development of this branch of the science of language.

Problems of word-formation categoricity are considered in dissertation research of recent decades, in which the ideas of cognitive science continue to develop. Such studies are inextricably linked with the theory of word-formation categoricity, since word-formation categories have “particular relevance for the reconstruction of the JCM”

In the work of E.P.Kadkalova, published in the collective monograph “Dynamics of semantic-word-formation subsystems of the Russian language”, examines the types of relationships between word-formation models of one word-formation category: synonymy, competition, parallelism.

Thus, a wide variety of word-formation models of the category of femininity inevitably leads to the distribution of models according to the original basis, according to conceptually significant semantic components, etc. The study of relationships between models of one word-formation category seems to be an important task of modern word-formation science.

In 2014, a monograph by V.A.Kosova “Word-formation categories of the Russian language: problems of theory”, which examines the theoretical problems of word-formation

categories: the relationship with other linguistic categories and with the categories of linguistic thinking. The work generalizes and develops the idea of the linguistic nature of this phenomenon; word-formation category is considered in the light of concepts categorization of mental and linguistic content, the systemic properties of the word-formation category are analyzed in detail in terms of the content plan and the expression plan. In addition to V.A.Kosova carried out an analysis and systematization of scientific literature on this topic from the moment the word-formation category was identified as a linguistic unit to the present.

In recent years, the study by linguists of categorical word-formation semantics and the means of its expression continues. First of all, the derivational categories of nouns are subject to a holistic analysis: thus, in 2018, a dissertation research by I.V. Fufaeva about the competition of expressive diminutives with neutral nouns, in which Russian expressive diminutives are presented as a word-formation category and their word-formation meanings are classified. In his work, the author proceeds from the principles of describing the word-formation category set out in the works of G.P. Neshchimenko and T.I.Vendina: a word-formation category is understood as “a homogeneous hierarchized macrosystem, including as system-forming components single-order isofunctional word-formation types, fastened by the identity of word-formation meaning and the identity of the formant’s classification affiliation”.

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